

Review—Ruthenium as Diffusion Barrier Layer in Electronic Interconnects: Current Literature with a Focus on Electrochemical Deposition Methods

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Ruthenium is one of the most promising candidates to replace tantalum and titanium based diffusion barrier layers in microelectronics. Its unique properties allow the deposition of ultrathin layers with controlled thickness by means of a wide variety of different techniques. Ruthenium barriers are characterized by good thermal stability, low resistivity and great adherence. Moreover, the copper filling deposited during the Damascene process can be directly applied on the barrier without the need of a seed layer. As a consequence of the industrial interest in developing new ruthenium based interconnects technologies, a significant literature has been produced in the last few years. The scope of the present work is to collect and analyze the literature on the topic, investigating in this way the technologies developed in the past and the current development stage of ruthenium based barrier layers. Due to their multiple advantages, a special focus is devoted to the manufacturing of ruthenium diffusion limiters by means of wet electrochemical processes.

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One of the most important revolutions occurred in the last decades in the field of electronic interconnects for ultra large scale integration (ULSI) is probably the switching from aluminum to copper as manufacturing material and the introduction of low-k dielectrics.¹⁻⁴ These innovations boosted the continuous scale down of minimum feature size required to match Moore's law.⁵ As a matter of fact, miniaturization of transistors and other active components proceeds to a much higher speed than interconnects, which thus constitute the real bottleneck for ULSI.⁶ Integrated circuits (ICs) manufacturers require an improved interconnects density in a reduced number of layers, which is in contrast with the need of keeping under control RC delay of circuits.⁷ Moreover, the recent introduction of 3D ICs with multiple stacked active layers⁸ makes interconnects even more vital. It is thus evident that, due to the large economic and social impact of the electronics industry, improving metallic interconnects is one of the leading topic in modern research on electronics. From the materials point of view, copper guarantees, with respect to the aluminum, a significantly lower resistivity (which implies less power dissipation and lower RC delays) and an improved resistance to electromigration.^{9,10} Moreover, RC delay and power dissipation can be further decreased by using low-k dielectrics layers, typically Si based materials or polymeric composites.^{11,12} The introduction of copper interconnects on Si wafer, however, is accompanied by a major problem: interdiffusion. Cu atoms quickly interdiffuse in Si^{13,14} or in the dielectric¹⁴ between the lines, and for this reason a diffusion barrier layer^{2,3,15} is typically required to avoid dielectric leakage. Barrier layers encapsulate copper vias and prevent interdiffusion. Many materials,^{2,3} applied normally via sputtering or chemical vapor deposition, have been employed as diffusion limiters. Such materials, however, are characterized by some drawbacks: poor step coverage in the case of sputtering and limited adherence of the electroplated Cu layer.¹⁶ Finally, state-of-the-art barrier layers are typically poorly conductive, making difficult Cu electrodeposition without the addition of an evaporated Cu seed layer.²

Recently, ruthenium has been proposed as potential material for barrier layers realization. This hard metal,^{17,18} characterized by a high chemical inertness and by a dark gray color, is used in many industrial applications. It is used, both pure and in combination with other elements, in the production of thin layers for aesthetic appli-

cations in jewelry and luxury goods manufacturing. Due to its hardness, it is satisfactorily applied in the wear protection of electrical contacts.^{19,20} Ruthenium in its metallic form,^{21,22} as oxide²³⁻²⁵ or as metallic complex^{26,27} is a good catalysts for many industrial reactions. Moreover, ruthenium oxide is also widely investigated as functional material for supercapacitors.^{28,29} Finally, ruthenium presents some of the main desired characteristics for barrier layers: absence of intermetallics in the Cu-Ru phase diagram³⁰ and good adhesion to Cu.³¹ The latter property allows direct Cu electrodeposition, avoiding the need of a Cu seed layer. For these reasons, it is widely investigated as potential diffusion barrier in Cu/low-k liners technology. Together with other innovative materials, like Co alloys,^{32,33} ruthenium is a promising candidate to replace current state-of-the-art diffusion barrier technologies.

A considerable amount of research has been carried out in the last decades on the production of ruthenium based diffusion barriers. It is therefore useful to provide a critical review of the current state-of-the-art on the topic. On these premises, the present paper has been written. In its first part, the manuscript describes what are barrier layers for Cu based interconnect, how they are nowadays produced, what are the main limitations and drawbacks of the barrier materials employed and why ruthenium can overcome such limitations. In the second part of the manuscript, manufacturing techniques for Ru thin layers are discussed. In this section, the focus of the discussion is placed on wet electrochemical techniques due to their advantages over other techniques: high scalability, lower cost and high productivity. In the final part of the work, an extensive review of existing literature references on Ru as barrier layer is presented. Also in this case, a special emphasis is dedicated to wet manufactured barrier layers. The treatise is not focused only on the deposition of thin Ru films and their performances as diffusion limiters, but is extended also to the electrodeposition challenges of Cu on Ru, to the chemical mechanical polishing (CMP) of Ru/Cu and to some emerging technologies that make use of full Ru based interconnects. To establish a connection between the world of research and the industrial practice, also some important patents released in the last few years are mentioned in the manuscript.

Electronic Interconnects and Diffusion Barrier Layers

Electronic interconnects.—In a standard IC, active components are built in the front end of line (FEOL), the region of the device

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Figure 1. General structure of an IC with BEOL evidenced (a); SEM section of an Intel Broadwell architecture IC with interconnects clearly visible (b).

in which transistors and other devices are directly patterned on the Si substrate.^{4,34} At the end of the microfabrication process, each active component requires to be connected with many others to form electrical circuits. The only way to accomplish this task is to build a second region in the IC, the back end of line (BEOL),⁴ which contains electrical interconnects. Such structures, as evident from Figure 1a, are placed on many different levels for space saving reasons. Figure 1b depicts a real example, the SEM section of an Intel Broadwell³⁵ architecture IC, where the different interconnects layers are clearly visible in the BEOL. Horizontal interconnects are normally called lines and are organized on many levels, progressively numbered starting from the FEOL. Vertical interconnects, linking together different lines, are normally called vias. A peculiar kind of structure is the through-silicon-via (TSV), which completely crosses the silicon wafer to connect one side with the other. TSVs are characterized by considerable dimensions and aspect ratios with respect to lines present in the BEOL and they are vital for multiple chips staking in the 3D integration process.^{4,8} An example of TSVs running through a silicon chip is visible in Figure 2a.

Until 1997, IC interconnects were produced using aluminum in a subtractive etching process.² In 1997, IBM³⁴ introduced the use of copper interconnects, making possible the production of smaller and faster ICs. Contrarily to aluminum, copper interconnects are produced with a peculiar technology involving many different steps: the Damascene process.^{4,36} In this technology, copper is deposited via superconformal electrodeposition³⁷ in the patterned interconnects and the excess material is subsequently removed employing the chemical-mechanical polishing (CMP) technique.^{3,38} From the technological point of view, the first reason for the Al to Cu technological upgrade is the improved conductivity of copper, higher than aluminum. Lines conductivity governs the global RC time delay of the circuit, as described by Equation 1.⁴

$$\tau = RCL^2 \quad [1]$$

Figure 2. SEM section of a chip showing three TSVs connecting the BEOL to the back side of the silicon wafer (a); SEM section of a TSV internally covered with a diffusion barrier layer (b).

where τ is the circuit delay, R is the line resistance, C is the line-to-line capacitance and L is the length of the line. In particular, R is expressed by Equation 2.

$$R = \frac{\rho L}{HW} \quad [2]$$

where ρ is the resistivity, H is the height of the line and W its width. C is defined by Equation 3.

$$C = \frac{\epsilon WL}{T} \quad [3]$$

where ϵ is the dielectric constant of the insulator between the lines and T is the spacing between the lines. It appears evident that a decrease in material resistivity leads to a decrease in RC delay. Moreover, the use of low resistivity materials is a major requirement in modern electronic industry due to Moore's law, which drives down the dimensions of the active components and of the interconnects between them. If H and W decrease, R obviously increases. For this reason, limiting resistivity is vital to contain RC delay. The second reason for choosing copper in place of aluminum is connected to its superior resistance to electromigration.³⁹ Copper interconnects are more resistant to this degradation mechanism.^{9,40} Finally, resistivity also determines thermal power dissipation, according to Joule's first law (Equation 4).

$$P = I^2 R \quad [4]$$

where P is the dissipated power and I is the current circulating in the line. Decreasing resistivity also makes possible thus a better control of IC temperature.

Another approach useful to decrease RC delay is the usage of low- k materials³ between the lines. RC delay depends also on C (Equation 1), which in turn is connected to the dielectric constant of the material (Equation 3). For this reason, substitution of silicon dioxide

as dielectric present between the interconnects with other materials can significantly reduce RC delay. Initially, due to their very low dielectric constant, polymer based materials were tested.^{12,41,42} Polymers, however, are characterized by mechanical properties typically not compatible with ULSI micromachining. For this reason, other materials were investigated. These include, for example, fluorine-doped Si oxides⁴³ (F-SiO₂), carbon-doped Si oxides⁴⁴ (SiCOH) or porous carbon-doped Si oxides⁴⁵ (p-SiCOH).

Barrier layers.—Copper interconnects, in all cases, require the presence of a barrier between the metal and the dielectric to avoid Cu interdiffusion and subsequent penetration in the dielectric. If Cu atoms enter the dielectric, they may create deep trap states or shortcuts in case of reagglomeration to form Cu particles,³ with the concrete risk of dielectric leakage. Moreover, Cu forms brittle silicides with Si,¹³ which may cause expansion and semiconductor contamination. Thin layers (called barrier layers) are therefore deposited between the dielectric and the copper to completely encapsulate the lines and isolate them.^{2-4,15,46,47} Figure 2 depicts the typical appearance of TSVs observed via SEM and the position of the barrier layer inside a single TSV.

The requirements for a diffusion limiting layer are many:^{3,48} it must provide mechanical stability and good adhesion to the copper deposited on top, it must not readily form intermetallics with copper, it must present a low diffusion coefficient for Cu atoms and it should be characterized by a resistivity as low as possible. The latter requirement is useful because barrier layers become part of the interconnects, and for this reason their contribution to total resistance must be considered in Equation 2. More specifically, a certain percentage of the eight H and width W of the line is constituted of barrier material, which reduces the fraction of highly conductive copper. For this reason, it is evident that the best scenario is to have barrier layers as thin as possible and as conductive as possible. To accomplish this, however, shielding properties of the materials employed should be very high to compensate the reduced thickness. Only a few classes of materials are suitable as barrier layers. These include some compounds of general structure Me-N, Me-C, Me-O, Me-Si and Me-B (where Me is typically a refractory metal with high melting point).³ The most widely used materials belonging to this class are TiN,^{49,50} TaN^{51,52} and double layers of Ta/TaN^{53,54} and Ti/TiN.⁵⁵ Another class of materials employed includes metallic alloys, generally including W³ or other refractory metals. Notable examples for this category are WN⁵⁶ and TiW.⁵⁷ All these materials are however characterized by the same drawbacks: relatively high resistivity and limited adhesion for electrodeposited copper layers. The latter is particularly critical for final adhesion of the layers to the FEOL and, to prevent detachment, a copper seed layer is normally deposited via physical vapor deposition (PVD),⁵⁸ chemical vapor deposition (CVD),⁵⁸ atomic layer deposition (ALD)⁵⁹ or electroless plating⁶⁰ between the barrier and the electrodeposited copper line. PVD, CVD and ALD are also normally used to deposit the barrier layers on top of the dielectric.

Many examples of alternative barrier layers have been developed during the last decades of industrial research. These include self assembled monolayers (SAM)⁶¹ based, polymeric based⁶² or even graphene based⁶³ barrier layers. To overcome cited limitations, however, the most promising substitutes are the ones based on pure non-refractory metals and their alloys, which have attracted many research efforts. These metals, to act as efficient diffusion barriers, must be characterized by good bonding properties with respect to copper (to avoid the need of copper seed layers), low resistivity and limited solubility with copper. Notable examples are Co^{32,64} and Ru, both pure and as alloys.

Ruthenium as barrier material.—Ru in particular, the subject of the present review, is a very interesting material due to its unique properties, cited in the introductory part and resumed in Table I. Of particular interest is its resistivity, higher than copper but orders of magnitude lower than other barrier materials based on metal/non-metal alloys. Moreover, it is relatively inert, it presents a good bonding strength

Table I. Physical properties of Ru.

Element	Ru
Atomic number	44
Atomic weight	101.7 g/mol
Electronic structure	(Kr)4d ⁷ 5s ¹
Crystal structure	Hexagonal close-packed (HCP) below 1030°C
Space group	194: P6 ₃ /mmc
Lattice constants (20°C)	a = 2.7058 Å; c = 4.2819 Å; c/a = 1.5824 Å
Density (20°C)	12.4 g/cm ³
Melting point	2334°C
Resistivity (polycrystalline; 23°C)	7.4 μΩ cm
Electron mean free path (25°C)	6.59 (perpendicular to the hcp hexagonal axis); 4.88 (parallel to the hcp hexagonal axis)

(making it a directly plateable barrier)⁶⁵ and low miscibility with electrodeposited copper. The latter statement can be verified observing the Cu-Ru phase diagram,³⁰ in which the two metals are practically immiscible up to the respective melting temperatures. When extremely thin, however, Ru can lose its barrier properties above 300°C.⁶⁶ The most obvious solution to improve Ru barrier properties without losing direct plateability and low resistivity is the coupling with a TaN layer.⁶⁷ Another possibility is the addition of alloying elements, like P or C, to Ru.³ Examples of these approaches are provided in the last part of the review.

Deposition Methods for Ruthenium Thin Layers

Dry deposition methods.—Like in the case of state-of-the-art barrier layers, like Ta/TaN, also Ru can be easily obtained employing the three main classes of thin films deposition dry methods in most of their variants: PVD, CVD and ALD. PVD can be used to deposit both pure Ru and Ru alloys⁶⁸ at the desired thickness. However, as widely acknowledged, PVD suffers from strong shadow effects⁶⁹ and may result inadequate for high aspect ratio vias. CVD, on the contrary, is able to provide highly conformal Ru⁷⁰ and Ru alloys⁷¹ films, with good purity if suitable precursors are employed.⁷² Such chemical precursors, however, are often highly toxic, making alternative techniques for thin films deposition highly desirable. The same drawback is valid in the case of ALD, a peculiar form of CVD that allows extreme control over thickness and purity of the obtained Ru layers.^{73,74}

Electrochemical deposition methods.—Another possibility to deposit thin Ru layers is the usage of wet deposition methods. In recent times, many PVD or CVD processes for metals deposition have been substituted or enhanced with techniques like electrodeposition⁷⁵ or electroless deposition.⁷⁶ Wet methodologies are characterized by low cost, good scalability and high throughput.⁷⁵ For these reasons, they adapt well to the microelectronics industry. Copper electrolytic and electroless deposition are already in use in the case of the cited Damascene process. In recent years, however, the research has seen the development of wet deposition techniques also suitable for the direct production of barrier layers. Such diffusion barriers are based on the already cited non-refractory metals and their alloys. The deposition technique employed is, for this application, almost exclusively electroless plating (due to its high conformity) and the materials deposited are typically compounds of phosphorus and boron with one or more metals. Some examples investigated in the past are: CoP,⁷⁷ CoB,⁷⁸ NiCoP,⁷⁷ NiP,⁷⁷ NiReP,⁷⁹ NiCrB⁸⁰ or NiPB.⁸¹ Also in the case of Ru, wet deposition processes can easily yield good quality metallic layers with controlled thickness. Ru electrodeposition is typically carried out in acidic aqueous solutions⁸²⁻⁸⁴ containing ruthenium in the form of the binuclear nitrido-bridged complex^{85,86} [RU₂NCl₈(H₂O)₂]³⁻. By using this class of electrolytes, compact layers of Ru can be successfully plated up to few micron thickness. Other plating baths

Figure 3. SEM of Ru layers on Si after electrodeposition from a solution of BMIPF₆ + 4mM RuCl₃ at -2V vs. Pt/Pt(II). Deposition times: (a) 10min, (b) 1h and (c) 2h. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 95.

formulations are available in literature,⁸⁷ but the nitride-bridged complex containing electrolyte is the only one presenting commercial relevance. An interesting process, especially for microelectronics, is electrochemical ALD (EALD). With this technique, monolayers and controlled multilayers of Ru can be easily obtained.⁸⁸

Recently, new electrolytes based on ionic liquids⁸⁹ have been introduced for the electrodeposition of many metals⁹⁰⁻⁹³ including ruthenium.⁹⁴⁻⁹⁸ These novel electrolytes present some advantages with respect to aqueous solutions: large potential windows, limited hydrogen evolution, low vapor pressure and improved metallic salts solubility.⁹³ Moreover, their limited aggressiveness toward delicate substrates allows electrodeposition on materials that are in many cases impossible to process in water solutions. An example is Ru electrodeposition on Si,^{94,95} which is almost impossible to coat with any metal with aqueous based electrodeposition. Figure 3 depicts the result obtained by Raz et al.⁹⁵ in plating Si with Ru thin layers.

Ru layers can be deposited, also on nonconductive layers like the dielectrics used in microelectronics, also employing electroless deposition. Ruthenium electroless deposition is a challenging process due to the peculiar electrochemical properties of this metal. In fact, Ru presents oxidation states in the range 0/8 and -2. The presence of a great number of oxidation states increases the possibility

Figure 4. TEM micrographs of Ru on TaN before and after annealing, showing partial formation of TaSi intermetallics. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 105.

of disproportionation reactions occurring in the electrolyte, leading to unstable deposition (or no deposition at all). Deposition of this metal have been demonstrated from different baths, typically mildly or strongly alkaline.⁹⁹⁻¹⁰⁴ Hydrazine, sodium boron hydride and sodium hypophosphite have all been used as reducing agents.

Ru Based Barrier Layers

Ru barriers from PVD, CVD and ALD.—A great number of literature examples is available on Ru barrier layers deposited from PVD, CVD or ALD, since these techniques are the ones typically used in current microelectronics industry (for this reason, a considerable know-how on their use is available). As significant example, Qu et al.¹⁰⁵ deposited ultrathin Ru layers on TaN and verified their barrier properties after annealing (Figure 4). They demonstrated that layers of Ru having thickness below 10 nm can be easily deposited via ion beam sputtering and that these layers, when combined with TaN, can resist interdiffusion up to 450°C. Wen et al.⁷⁴ deposited Ru on TiN via ALD, obtaining also in this case good thermal resistance of the final structure. Arunagiri et al.⁶⁵ deposited by sputtering 5 nm of Ru as barrier layers, without TaN or TiN, to test the performances of a single Ru layer. With respect to the work by Qu et al., it was observed that the layers failed at much lower temperatures, around 300°C. Ru has been sputtered also on alternative barrier layers like WN, like in the case of the work by Sari et al.¹⁰⁶ In this case, high breakdown temperatures were achieved (750°C) with 7 nm of Ru on 8 nm of WN. From the industrial point of view, many patents are available on PVD deposited Ru layers for interconnects.^{107,108}

Besides PVD, CVD and ALD are widely used techniques for thin Ru films deposition. ALD, in particular, is very attractive due to its conformity and to the precise control (down to the monoatomic layer) over thickness. Choi et al.¹⁰⁹ and Xie et al.¹¹⁰ prepared Ru barrier layers on TaN by employing plasma enhanced ALD (PEALD). Such layers were able to withstand temperatures higher than 400°C, with catastrophic failure at 660°C. PEALD of Ru on TiN has been attempted as well by Wen et al.⁷⁴ and by Kwon et al.^{111,112} with good results. Patents for industrial CVD^{113,114} and ALD^{115,116} processes, like in the case of PVD, are widely present in current literature.

As already discussed, and as the examples discussed confirm, ultrathin pure Ru layers are inefficient above 300°C. Thicker layers are more stable, up to 700°C,¹¹⁷ but impractical as competitive barrier layers. To improve their stability, alloying elements are typically added. Perng et al.¹¹⁸ and Shin et al.,¹¹⁹ employing controlled diffusion and CVD respectively, manufactured P alloyed Ru single layers able to reach temperatures over 550°C without significant ruthenium silicide formation. Gases dissolved in the Ru layer, similarly to alloying elements, evidenced positive effects on barrier properties of the final coating. This effect was demonstrated by Damayanti et al.¹²⁰ in the case of N dissolved in Ru. From the point of view of Ru alloys usage, some patents on ruthenium silicides barrier layers are available.^{121,122}

Ru barriers from electrochemical deposition.—From the wet manufacturing point of view, less examples of barrier layer production

Figure 5. Section of electroless deposited Ru on Ta covered with an electroless Cu seed layer (a); SEM of a TSV before and after application of Ru/Cu. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 123.

are available. The topic, however, is of great interest due to the characteristic advantages of wet metallization. Two fundamental works from this point of view, which clearly demonstrate the potentiality of electroless Ru barrier layer deposition coupled with electroless seed copper plating, are the ones published by Seo et al.¹²³ in 2016 and by Song et al.¹²⁴ in 2011. Seo et al., in particular, deposited Ru via electroless plating from an alkaline solution inside Ta covered TSVs having aspect ratio 11. Subsequently, they deposited Cu employing an alkaline electroless copper bath. Figure 5 depicts the result obtained. Conformal plating in all TSV regions was successfully achieved, with good coverage and deposit quality. Ru was deposited on Si also by galvanic displacement electroless plating,¹²⁵ achieving metallic films usable as barrier layers. Electroless deposition have been employed for barrier layers deposition also in a patent recently registered by Boyd et al.¹²⁶

Besides electroless deposition, also electrolytic plating have been investigated for Ru barrier layer deposition. Kim et al.¹²⁷ demonstrated the feasibility of Ru deposition from a solution containing the classical N-bridged complex of ruthenium nitrosyl chloride. They formed Ru barriers on Ti and TiN coated Si and subsequently applied Cu via electrolytic deposition.

Properties of Ru barrier layers and failure mechanism.—Diffusion limiting efficiency of pure Ru layers, as any other barrier layers, strongly depends on thickness and on heat exposure time. 5 nm thick layers can resist up to 300°C for 10 minutes,⁶⁵ but 22 nm thick ones withstand temperatures higher than 450°C¹²⁸ for the same time. Also barrier layer crystallinity plays a fundamental role in determining interdiffusion resistance. In presence of grain boundaries, Cu interdiffusion in Ru is strongly enhanced. The 5 nm thick barrier layers deposited by Arunagiri et al.,⁶⁵ for example, were found to be amorphous, an optimal condition to avoid grain boundary diffusion. Many alloys of ruthenium with another substance, like P or C, present improved interdiffusion resistance thanks exactly to the amorphization induced by the presence of the second element on Ru. Damayanti et al.¹¹⁷ characterized the failure of Ru layers between Cu and Si in the 10–30 nm range. Failure happened due to silicide Ru₂Si₃ formation, resulting in rapid deterioration of the conductivity and of the barrier properties of the layer. At very high temperatures (> 800°C), a Cu₃Si phase formed directly in the silicon substrate, protruding from the Ru layer. In some cases, Ru delamination from the substrate is possible as well.¹²⁸ Early signs of single layer Ru barrier failure can be detected by sheet resistivity measurements, since ruthenium silicides present resistance higher than pure Ru. Figure 6 describes typical values of sheet resistance in the case of Ru on Ta and TaN.¹²⁹ It also shows how, at high temperature in the case of Ru on Si, sheet resistance increased of one order of magnitude in the experiment performed. Apparently, Ru forms silicides with Si when directly plated on Si. If

Figure 6. Sheet resistance variation for Ru, Ru/Ta and Ru/TaN layers as a function of annealing temperature. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 129.

Ta is placed in between, no silicides form up to 900°C, and this is the reason of the superior stability of Ru/Ta or Ru/TaN barrier layers with respect to single Ru coatings. The comparatively low resistivity of Ru barriers allows a significant reduction of final line resistance. The possibility of reducing interconnects resistivity by using Ru/Ta or Ru/TaN interconnects has been demonstrated by Van der Veen et al.,¹³⁰ which evidenced that Ru based interconnects greatly outperform not only current state-of-the-art technologies but also Co based alternative barriers. Yang et al.¹³¹ investigated also the electromigration resistance of Ru barriers. With respect to the classical Ta/TaN bilayer, no electromigration degradation was observed in the case of a Ru/TaN line.

Damascene process on Ru barrier layers.—The first step of the Damascene process requires the deposition of copper via electrolytic superconformal deposition.^{4,37} In the case of Ru barriers, the Damascene process presents some peculiarities. For this reason, it is fundamental to investigate how copper deposits on Ru barrier layers. Cu/Ru interface properties strongly influence final resistivity and adhesion between the layers. Typically, Cu is characterized by a good adhesion on Ru.¹³² This property, which allows direct metallization, is one of the main reasons for the use of Ru barrier layers. Kim et al.¹³³ individuated the reason for this behavior in the great affinity and low interface energy of Cu on Ru substrates, demonstrating that the contact angle of Cu on Ru is three times lower than that of Cu on Ta (43° vs. 123°). Chyan et al.¹³⁴ and Guo et al.¹³⁵ studied the nucleation mechanism of Cu on Ru and oxidized Ru respectively. Guo et al., in particular, evidenced that Cu nucleates and grows also on oxidized Ru, which is a common condition in metallization. Also Akolkar et al. studied Cu nucleation on Ru and verified that Cu can be directly seed electroplated on Ru covered features.¹³⁶ Different authors^{31,137–140} demonstrated that, as a direct consequence of the good adhesion between Ru and Cu, TSVs and lines superfilling can be achieved without substantial problems. Some peculiar superfilling processes on Ru layers have been patented as well.¹⁴¹

The second step of the Damascene process is CMP, which has been successfully employed in the case of Ru barriers.^{142,143} As in the case of any other interconnects technology, specific CMP slurries and parameters must be specifically developed, but CMP of the Ru/Cu couple presents a peculiar challenge with respect to state-of-the-art barriers like Ta/TaN. Ru, in fact, is a highly conductive metal in contact with a less noble metal like copper. For this reason, galvanic corrosion is highly possible during CMP. Chou et al.¹⁴⁴ and Jiang et al.¹⁴⁵ characterized the galvanic corrosion phenomenon taking place during CMP of Ru/Cu, demonstrating that the corrosion rate is considerable in KIO₄ slurries not adequately additivated with inhibitors.

Due to the relevance of the problem, corrosion control during CMP is the main subject of many papers.^{146,147} Ru/Cu CMP is also a topic of great industrial relevance, and, for this reason, some patents regarding slurries and operating parameters have been registered recently.¹⁴⁸

Full ruthenium interconnects.—Recently, the possibility to manufacture full Ru interconnect have been investigated. Ru as line manufacturing material is advantageous primarily in the case of ultrasmall interconnects. In this case, the enhanced scattering of electrons leads to a resistivity increase¹⁴⁹ that can seriously affect RC delay. Replacement of Cu with a high melting metal, like Ru, can improve performances. Moreover, in the case of ultrasmall interconnects, it can be technologically unfeasible the employment of the normal barrier layer/Cu core structure due to the high resistivity of the resulting line. As already discussed, when interconnect dimensions shrink, the barrier layer accounts for a considerable fraction of the total line section. This effect justifies the use of interconnects completely made of a material presenting low resistivity and barrier properties.¹⁵⁰ Finally, full Ru interconnects can mitigate the electromigration phenomenon typical of Cu interconnects thanks to the limited electromigration pre-deposition of Ru. For these reasons, realization of nanometric Ru interconnects has been attempted by Zhang et al.¹⁵¹ and Dutta et al.¹⁵² Full Ru interconnects production is also the subject of a recent paper by Yu et al.,¹⁵³ whereas Wen et al.¹⁵⁴ recently demonstrated the superior electromigration resistance of full Ru lines.

Conclusions and Perspectives

The great number of papers, also very recent, on Ru as barrier layer demonstrates that the topic is strategic in modern electronics industry. However, Ru is not currently employed in real interconnects applications at the industry level. From this point of view, the necessity to fully characterize its properties as barrier layer and to optimize dedicated Damascene and CMP prevented the immediate diffusion of Ru based diffusion limiters. It is highly probable, nevertheless, that in the next future the electronics industry will have to prepare for the introduction of Ru containing interconnects. The present review evidenced all the potentialities of Ru as barrier layer and described the main fabrication techniques that can find application in microelectronics. Moreover, a number of practical examples for barriers manufacturing was provided. The particular focus posed on electrochemical deposition for Ru barrier layers production evidenced the great number of possibilities that is possible to exploit by employing techniques like electroless or electrolytic plating. This approach will also have to further implement the chemistry of the electrolytes in order to tailor the deposition process to achieve a controlled crystalline structure of the ruthenium layers, to overcome the possible co-deposition of oxides and the tendency of ruthenium electrochemical deposition processes to be intrinsically limited in terms of thickness.

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References

- X. W. Lin and D. Pramanik, *Solid State Technol.*, **41**, 63 (1998).
- Y. Shacham-Diamand, T. Osaka, M. Datta, and T. Ohba, *Advanced nanoscale ULSI interconnects: fundamentals and applications*, Springer, (2009).
- M. Baklanov, P. S. Ho, and E. Zschech, *Advanced interconnects for ULSI technology*, John Wiley & Sons, (2012).
- S. Franssila, *Introduction to microfabrication*, John Wiley & Sons, (2010).
- S. E. Thompson and S. Parthasarathy, *Mater. today*, **9**, 20 (2006).
- M. T. Bohr, in *Electron Devices Meeting, 1995. IEDM'95., International*, p. 241, IEEE (1995).
- I. Ciofi et al., *IEEE Trans. Electron Devices*, **63**, 2488 (2016).
- C. S. Tan, R. J. Gutmann, and L. R. Reif, *Wafer level 3-D ICs process technology*, Springer Science & Business Media, (2009).
- T. Frank et al., *Microelectron. Reliab.*, **53**, 17 (2013).
- R. L. Jackson et al., *Solid State Technol.*, **41**, 49 (1998).
- D. Shamiryan, T. Abell, F. Iacopi, and K. Maex, *Mater. Today*, **7**, 34 (2004).
- J. Yuan, S. Yao, and P. Poulin, in *Polymer Nanocomposites*, p. 3, Springer (2016).
- R. W. Olesinski and G. J. Abbaschian, *Bull. Alloy Phase Diagrams*, **7**, 170 (1986).
- D. Gupta, *Mater. Chem. Phys.*, **41**, 199 (1995).
- M.-A. Nicolet, *Thin Solid Films*, **52**, 415 (1978).
- A. Dulkin et al., *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. A Vacuum, Surfaces, Film.*, **29**, 41514 (2011).
- S. E. Livingstone, in *Pergamon Texts in Inorganic Chemistry*, vol. **25**, p. 1163, Pergamon (1973).
- E. of E. Britannica, <https://www.britannica.com/science/ruthenium>.
- P. C. Hydes, *Platin. Met. Rev.*, **24**, 50 (1980).
- L. Shishkina, O. Lokshanova, and S. Karabanov, *Coatings*, **2**, 1 (2012).
- T. Umegaki, Y. Enomoto, and Y. Kojima, *Catal. Sci. Technol.*, **6**, 409 (2016).
- S. Iqbal et al., *ACS Catal.*, **5**, 5047 (2015).
- J.-J. Jow, H.-J. Lee, H.-R. Chen, M.-S. Wu, and T.-Y. Wei, *Electrochim. Acta*, **52**, 2625 (2007).
- H. Over, *Chem. Rev.*, **112**, 3356 (2012).
- H. R. Zare, S. H. Hashemi, and A. Benvidi, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, **668**, 182 (2010).
- R. A. Molla et al., *J. Organomet. Chem.*, **776**, 170 (2015).
- M. J. Stark, D. T. Tang, N. P. Rath, and E. B. Bauer, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, **59**, 873 (2018).
- Y. R. Ahn, M. Y. Song, S. M. Jo, C. R. Park, and D. Y. Kim, *Nanotechnology*, **17**, 2865 (2006).
- B.-O. Park, C. D. Lokhande, H.-S. Park, K.-D. Jung, and O.-S. Joo, *J. Mater. Sci.*, **39**, 4313 (2004).
- Y. Du, in *Binary Evaluations: Cu-Ru*, G. Effenberg, Editor, MSI, Materials Science International Services GmbH, Stuttgart (2002).
- D. Josell, D. Wheeler, C. Witt, and T. P. Moffat, *Electrochem. Solid-State Lett.*, **6**, C143 (2003).
- X. Wang et al., *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.*, **50**, 405306 (2017).
- H. Shimizu, K. Sakoda, and Y. Shimogaki, *Microelectron. Eng.*, **106**, 91 (2013).
- M. J. Madou, *Fundamentals of microfabrication: the science of miniaturization*, CRC press, (2002).
- <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/design/personal-computers/platforms/broadwell-h/overview.html?wapkw=broadwell>.
- P. C. Andricacos, C. Uzoh, J. O. Dukovic, J. Horkans, and H. Deligianni, *IBM J. Res. Dev.*, **42**, 567 (1998).
- T. P. Moffat, D. Wheeler, W. H. Huber, and D. Josell, *Electrochem. Solid-State Lett.*, **4**, C26 (2001).
- M. R. Oliver, *Chemical-mechanical planarization of semiconductor materials*, Springer Science & Business Media, (2013).
- A. Christou, Ed., *Electromigration and electronic device degradation*, Wiley, (1993).
- J. C. Doan, J. C. Bravman, P. A. Flinn, and T. N. Marieb, *Microelectron. Reliab.*, **40**, 981 (2000).
- M. Morgen et al., *Annu. Rev. Mater. Sci.*, **30**, 645 (2000).
- K. Maex et al., *J. Appl. Phys.*, **93**, 8793 (2003).
- C. H. Ting and T. E. Seidel, *MRS Online Proc. Libr. Arch.*, **381** (1995).
- P. Verdonck et al., *Microelectron. Eng.*, **120**, 225 (2014).
- A. Grill, *J. Appl. Phys.*, **93**, 1785 (2003).
- P. S. Ho, *Thin Solid Films*, **96**, 301 (1982).
- R. S. Nowicki and M.-A. Nicolet, *Thin Solid Films*, **96**, 317 (1982).
- S. S. Wong et al., in *Interconnect Technology Conference, 1998. Proceedings of the IEEE 1998 International*, p. 107, IEEE (1998).
- S. Riedel, S. E. Schulz, J. Baumann, M. Rennau, and T. Gessner, *Microelectron. Eng.*, **55**, 213 (2001).
- M. Y. Kwak, D. H. Shin, T. W. Kang, and K. N. Kim, *Thin Solid Films*, **339**, 290 (1999).
- M. Hecker et al., *Thin Solid Films*, **414**, 184 (2002).
- T. Oku et al., *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, **99**, 265 (1996).
- N. Fréty, F. Bernard, J. Nazon, J. Sarrafin, and J.-C. Tedenac, *J. phase equilibria Diffus.*, **27**, 590 (2006).
- L. Y. Yang, D. H. Zhang, C. Y. Li, and P. D. Foo, *Thin Solid Films*, **462**, 176 (2004).
- M. Mändl, H. Hoffmann, and P. Kücher, *J. Appl. Phys.*, **68**, 2127 (1990).
- R. Ecke, S. E. Schulz, M. Hecker, and T. Gessner, *Microelectron. Eng.*, **64**, 261 (2002).
- S. Wang, S. Suthar, C. Hoefflich, and B. J. Burrow, *J. Appl. Phys.*, **73**, 2301 (1993).
- K. Weiss et al., *Microelectron. Eng.*, **50**, 433 (2000).
- T. Waechter et al., *Microelectron. Eng.*, **88**, 684 (2011).
- J. P. O'Kelly et al., *Microelectron. Eng.*, **50**, 473 (2000).
- A. Krishnamoorthy, K. Chanda, S. P. Murarka, G. Ramanath, and J. G. Ryan, *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, **78**, 2467 (2001).
- P. G. Ganesan, J. Gamba, A. Ellis, R. S. Kane, and G. Ramanath, *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, **83**, 3302 (2003).
- W. K. Morrow, S. J. Pearton, and F. Ren, *Small*, **12**, 120 (2016).
- T. Nogami et al., in *Interconnect Technology Conference (IITC), 2010 International*, p. 1, IEEE (2010).
- T. N. Arunagiri et al., *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, **86**, 1 (2005).
- J. Musschoot et al., *Microelectron. Eng.*, **87**, 1879 (2010).
- S. Kumar, D. Greenslit, T. Chakraborty, and E. T. Eisenbraun, *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. A Vacuum, Surfaces, Film.*, **27**, 572 (2009).
- D.-C. Peng, K.-C. Hsu, S.-W. Tsai, and J.-B. Yeh, *Microelectron. Eng.*, **87**, 365 (2010).
- D. M. Mattox, *Handbook of physical vapor deposition (PVD) processing*, William Andrew, (2010).
- M. L. Green, M. E. Gross, L. E. Papa, K. J. Schnoes, and D. Brasen, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **132**, 2677 (1985).

71. J. Shin et al., *Thin Solid Films*, **515**, 5298 (2007).
72. A. Schneider et al., *Chem. Vap. Depos.*, **13**, 389 (2007).
73. H. Wojcik et al., *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **159**, H166 (2012).
74. L. G. Wen et al., *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, **8**, 26119 (2016).
75. M. Schlesinger and M. Paunovic, *Modern electroplating*, John Wiley & Sons, (2011).
76. G. O. Mallory and J. B. Hajdu, *Electroless plating: fundamentals and applications*, William Andrew, (1990).
77. E. J. O'Sullivan et al., *IBM J. Res. Dev.*, **42**, 607 (1998).
78. T. Iseri et al., in *Electronics Packaging and iMAPS All Asia Conference (ICEP-IAAC), 2018 International Conference on*, p. 485, IEEE (2018).
79. T. Osaka, N. Takano, T. Kurokawa, and K. Ueno, *Electrochem. solid-state Lett.*, **5**, C7 (2002).
80. Y. Wang et al., *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, **396**, 333 (2017).
81. R. Bernasconi, A. Molazemhosseini, M. Cervati, S. Armini, and L. Magagnin, *J. Electron. Mater.*, **45**, 5449 (2016).
82. G. S. Reddy and P. Taimsalu, *Trans. IMF*, **47**, 187 (1969).
83. C. R. K. Rao and D. C. Trivedi, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, **249**, 613 (2005).
84. F. H. Reid and J. C. Blake, *Trans. IMF*, **38**, 45 (1961).
85. S. M. Karabanov and O. G. Lokshanova, *Russ. J. Appl. Chem.*, **81**, 1000 (2008).
86. E. A. Seddon and K. R. Seddon, *The Chemistry of Ruthenium*, Elsevier Science Inc., Amsterdam, (1984).
87. D. K. Oppedisano, L. A. Jones, T. Junk, and S. K. Bhargava, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **161**, D489 (2014).
88. C. Thambidurai, Y.-G. Kim, and J. L. Stickney, *Electrochim. Acta*, **53**, 6157 (2008).
89. M. Galiński, A. Lewandowski, and I. Stepniak, *Electrochim. Acta*, **51**, 5567 (2006).
90. R. Bernasconi et al., in *Progress and Developments in Ionic Liquids*, InTech (2017).
91. A. P. Abbott and K. J. McKenzie, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, **8**, 4265 (2006).
92. E. L. Smith, A. P. Abbott, and K. S. Ryder, *Chem. Rev.*, **114**, 11060 (2014).
93. F. Endres, A. Abbott, and D. MacFarlane, *Electrodeposition from ionic liquids*, John Wiley & Sons, (2017).
94. O. Mann, W. Freyland, O. Raz, and Y. Ein-Eli, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, **460**, 178 (2008).
95. O. Raz, G. Cohn, W. Freyland, O. Mann, and Y. Ein-Eli, *Electrochim. Acta*, **54**, 6042 (2009).
96. M. Jayakumar, K. A. Venkatesan, T. G. Srinivasan, and P. R. Vasudeva Rao, *Electrochim. Acta*, **54**, 6747 (2009).
97. M. Jayakumar, K. A. Venkatesan, R. Sudha, T. G. Srinivasan, and P. R. Vasudeva Rao, *Mater. Chem. Phys.*, **128**, 141 (2011).
98. R. Bernasconi, A. Lucotti, L. Nobili, and L. Magagnin, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **165**, D620 (2018).
99. Y. S. Chang and M. L. Chou, *J. Appl. Phys.*, **69**, 7848 (1991).
100. J.-Y. Chen, L.-Y. Wang, and P.-W. Wu, *Thin Solid Films*, **518**, 7245 (2010).
101. N. Xu et al., *J. Membr. Sci. Res.*, **1**, 73 (2015).
102. A. Joi, A. Ziemele, E. Norkus, L. Tamasauskaitė-Tamasiunaite, and Y. Dordi, in *Meeting Abstracts*, p. 898, The Electrochemical Society (2015).
103. J.-Y. Chen, Y.-C. Hsieh, L.-Y. Wang, and P.-W. Wu, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **158**, D463 (2011).
104. J.-Y. Chen, S.-L. Huang, P.-W. Wu, and P. Lin, *Thin Solid Films*, **529**, 426 (2013).
105. X.-P. Qu et al., *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, **88**, 151912 (2006).
106. W. Sari, T.-K. Eom, C.-W. Jeon, H. Sohn, and S.-H. Kim, *Electrochem. Solid-State Lett.*, **12**, H248 (2009).
107. K. H. Yoon, Y. C. Cha, S. H. Yu, H. F. Ahmad, and H. S. Wee, (2004).
108. J. Wang et al., (2006).
109. B. H. Choi et al., *Microelectron. Eng.*, **87**, 1391 (2010).
110. Q. Xie et al., *Thin Solid Films*, **517**, 4689 (2009).
111. O.-K. Kwon, S.-H. Kwon, H.-S. Park, and S.-W. Kang, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **151**, C753 (2004).
112. S.-H. Kwon, O.-K. Kwon, J.-S. Min, and S.-W. Kang, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **153**, G578 (2006).
113. M. Chang, S. Ganguli, and N. Maity, (2007).
114. S. Ganguli, K. Shah, N. Maity, and M. Chang, (2011).
115. W.-M. Li, (2005).
116. H. Kim and S. M. Rossnagel, (2006).
117. M. Damayanti, T. Sritharan, S. G. Mhaisalkar, E. Phoon, and L. Chan, *J. Mater. Res.*, **22**, 2505 (2007).
118. D.-C. Pong, J.-B. Yeh, and K.-C. Hsu, *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, **254**, 6059 (2008).
119. J. Shin et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **128**, 16510 (2006).
120. M. Damayanti, T. Sritharan, S. G. Mhaisalkar, and Z. H. Gan, *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, **88**, 44101 (2006).
121. B. A. Vaartstra and E. P. Marsh, (2013).
122. B. A. Vaartstra and E. P. Marsh, (2009).
123. S. Seo and B. Yoo, *J. Nanosci. Nanotechnol.*, **16**, 11267 (2016).
124. M. Song et al., *Sci. Adv. Mater.*, **3**, 932 (2011).
125. H. Philipsen and W. Monnens, *Electrochim. Acta*, **274**, 306 (2018).
126. D. A. Boyd and A. Li, (2014).
127. Y.-S. Kim et al., *Electrochem. solid-state Lett.*, **9**, C19 (2006).
128. R. Chan et al., *Electrochem. Solid-State Lett.*, **7**, G154 (2004).
129. J.-J. Tan, X.-P. Qu, Q. Xie, Y. Zhou, and G.-P. Ru, *Thin Solid Films*, **504**, 231 (2006).
130. M. H. van der Veen et al., in *2018 IEEE International Interconnect Technology Conference (IITC)*, p. 172, IEEE (2018).
131. C. C. Yang et al., *IEEE Electron Device Lett.*, **31**, 722 (2010).
132. M. W. Lane, C. E. Murray, F. R. McFeely, P. M. Vereecken, and R. Rosenberg, *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, **83**, 2330 (2003).
133. H. Kim et al., *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **152**, G594 (2005).
134. O. Chyan, T. N. Arunagir, and T. Ponnuswamy, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **150**, C347 (2003).
135. L. Guo, A. Radisic, and P. C. Seanson, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **153**, C840 (2006).
136. R. Akolkar et al., in *Interconnect Technology Conference and 2011 Materials for Advanced Metallization (IITC/MAM), 2011 IEEE International*, p. 1, IEEE (2011).
137. T. P. Moffat et al., *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, **153**, C37 (2006).
138. F. Inoue et al., *Electrochim. Acta*, **100**, 203 (2013).
139. T.-C. Kuo et al., *Microelectron. Eng.*, **162**, 27 (2016).
140. R. Akolkar, C.-C. Cheng, R. Chebiam, A. Fajardo, and V. Dubin, *ECS Trans.*, **2**, 13 (2007).
141. T. Weidman et al., (2006).
142. Cabot Microelectronics Corporation, *Ruthenium CMP Integration for Dual-Damascene Copper Interconnects*, (2010) https://www.cabotcmp.com/wp-content/uploads/CMC_Ruthenium_CMP_Integration.pdf.
143. R. R. Patlolla et al., *ECS J. Solid State Sci. Technol.*, **7**, P397 (2018).
144. Y.-S. Chou, S.-C. Yen, and K.-T. Jeng, *Mater. Chem. Phys.*, **162**, 477 (2015).
145. L. Jiang, Y. He, X. Lu, and J. Luo, in *Planarization/CMP Technology (ICPT), 2014 International Conference on*, p. 209, IEEE (2014).
146. K. Maruyama, M. Shiohara, K. Yamada, S. Kondo, and S. Saito, *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.*, **48**, 04C022 (2009).
147. B. C. Peethala, D. Roy, and S. V. Babu, *Electrochem. Solid-State Lett.*, **14**, H306 (2011).
148. Z. Liu, (2008).
149. E. H. Sondheimer, *Adv. Phys.*, **50**, 499 (2001).
150. K. Derbyshire, (2017) <https://semiengineering.com/ruthenium-liners-give-way-to-ruthenium-lines/>.
151. X. Zhang et al., in *Interconnect Technology Conference/Advanced Metallization Conference (IITC/AMC), 2016 IEEE International*, p. 31, IEEE (2016).
152. S. Dutta et al., *IEEE Electron Device Lett.*, **38**, 949 (2017).
153. K.-H. Yu, G. J. Leusink, C. Wajda, T. Ishizaka, and T. Hakamata, (2018).
154. L. G. Wen et al., in *Interconnect Technology Conference/Advanced Metallization Conference (IITC/AMC), 2016 IEEE International*, p. 34, IEEE (2016).